

TABLE 1—INFRARED SPECTRAL BANDS (cm⁻¹) OF THE COMPLEXES

Compd.	ν_{C-S}	ν_{Pd-Cl}	ν_{Pd-S}
PdCl ₂ (C ₆ H ₅ SCH ₃) ₂	727w	373s, 342s	298m
PdCl ₂ (<i>o</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄ SCH ₃) ₂	727w	362s	312s
PdCl ₂ (<i>m</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄ SCH ₃) ₂	727w	350ms	300ms
PdCl ₂ (<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄ SCH ₃) ₂	716mw	373s, 336s	288m
PdCl ₂ (<i>o</i> -BrC ₆ H ₄ SCH ₃) ₂	720m	356s	312m
PdCl ₂ (<i>m</i> -BrC ₆ H ₄ SCH ₃) ₂	732w	350s	300w
PdCl ₂ (<i>p</i> -BrC ₆ H ₄ SCH ₃) ₂	727s	373ms, 350s	281m
PdCl ₂ (<i>o</i> -IC ₆ H ₄ SCH ₃) ₂	726m	358ms	312ms
PdCl ₂ (<i>m</i> -IC ₆ H ₄ SCH ₃) ₂	738ms	360s	300m
PdCl ₂ (<i>p</i> -IC ₆ H ₄ SCH ₃) ₂	744mw	371m, 350s	265ms
PdCl ₂ (<i>o</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ SCH ₃) ₂	731ms	361s	312ms
PdCl ₂ (<i>m</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ SCH ₃) ₂	738s	346s	304mw
PdCl ₂ (<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ SCH ₃) ₂	724m	370m	326m
PdCl ₂ (<i>p</i> -COCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ SCH ₃) ₂	723ms	358s	312ms
PdCl ₂ (<i>o</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ SCH ₃) ₂	727mw	360s	312m
PdCl ₂ (<i>m</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ SCH ₃) ₂	724mw	350ms	297m
PdCl ₂ (<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ SCH ₃) ₂	720mw	363s	290mw
PdCl ₂ (2,6-di-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₃ SCH ₃) ₂	719mw	361s	319ms
PdCl ₂ (<i>o</i> -OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ SCH ₃) ₂	722m	362s, 335m	281m
PdCl ₂ (<i>m</i> -OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ SCH ₃) ₂	724w	350s	310m
PdCl ₂ (<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ SCH ₃) ₂	722mw	367m, 350s	277ms
PdCl ₂ (<i>o</i> -OHC ₆ H ₄ SCH ₃) ₂	725mw	358m, 337m	250w
PdCl ₂ (<i>p</i> -OHC ₆ H ₄ SCH ₃) ₂	724ms	356ms, 329w	250w
PdCl ₂ (<i>o</i> -COOH ₂ C ₆ H ₃ SCH ₃) ₂	724w	356s, 324w	310m
PdCl ₂ (<i>m</i> -COOH ₂ C ₆ H ₃ SCH ₃) ₂	720ms	354s	298ms
PdCl ₂ (<i>p</i> -COOH ₂ C ₆ H ₃ SCH ₃) ₂	720ms	374s, 334s	305w
PdCl ₂ (4-OCH ₃ -3-OH ₂ C ₆ H ₃ SCH ₃) ₂	719ms	351s	270mw
PdCl ₂ (3,5-di-CH ₃ -4-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₃ SCH ₃) ₂	724ms	374s, 334w	312vw

* In PdCl₂, ν_{Pd-Cl} = 337 cm⁻¹. vs = Very strong, s = strong, ms = medium strong, m = medium, mw = medium weak, w = weak, vw = very weak.

derivatives, the ν_{CSC} generally appears as a band of weak or moderate intensity in 702–673 cm⁻¹ region⁹. The increase in the ν_{CSC} is attributed to coordination from the sulphur atom.

Magnetic and Spectral Studies of Platinum(IV), Palladium(II) and Osmium(VI) Complexes with Thiodisuccinic Acid

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THE complexes of second and third row transition metal ions are interesting because of their enhanced stability, unusual magnetic properties and formation of bridges. The present communication deals with the preparation and characterisation of platinum(IV), palladium(II) and osmium(VI) complexes with thiodisuccinic acid, HOOCCH₂CH(COOH)SCH(COOH)CH₂COOH (hereafter, TDSA). TDSA contains one sulphur atom and four carboxylic groups and is capable of combining with metal ions in various polydentate modes.

Experimental

Thiodisuccinic acid (Evans Chemetics, Inc., New York) of 98.1% purity was used as such without

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TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Compd.	Colour	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)				Loss % : Found/ (Calcd.)	Decomp. temp. °C	Λ_M $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$
		C	H	S	Metal			
$[\text{Pt}_2(\text{C}_6\text{H}_6\text{O}_8\text{S})\text{Cl}_4]$	Greyish	12.25 (12.08)	0.75 (0.70)	4.16 (4.02)	24.18 (24.57)	—	265	22.80 ^c
$[\text{Pd}_2(\text{C}_6\text{H}_6\text{O}_8\text{S})] \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	Reddish brown	21.45 (19.45)	1.82 (1.62)	6.10 (6.48)	21.96 (21.62)	3.50 ^a (3.64)	195	15.30 ^c
$\text{Na}_4[(\text{OsO}_2)_2(\text{C}_6\text{H}_6\text{O}_8\text{S})(\text{OH})_4] \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Brownish black	10.91 (10.04)	3.27 (3.20)	3.45 (3.40)	89.77 (89.50)	8.86 ^b (9.41)	160	431.00 ^d

^a At 110°. ^b At 120°. ^c In DMSO. ^d In DMF.

further purification. All other chemicals used were of AR grade.

Preparation of complexes: The complexes of Pt^{IV} , Pd^{II} and Os^{VI} with TDSA were prepared as follows. An aqueous solutions of the metal chloride (except for the Os complex, where osmic acid was used, 0.2 M, 50 ml) were added to an equimolar solution of TDSA in aqueous phase. pH of the resulting mixtures were maintained at 8–10. In case of Pt^{IV} and Os^{VI} , the resulting mixtures were concentrated to 50 ml to yield greyish and brownish black solid complexes, respectively, on refrigeration for 2 days; but in case of Pd^{II} , the resulting mixture was heated on steam-bath for 2 h and concentrated to 50 ml and when cooled excess of acetone precipitated a dark reddish brown complex. The complexes were filtered, washed with ethanol, acetone and ether, and dried in vacuum over calcium chloride. These complexes were slightly soluble in water and common organic solvents. Analytical data are presented in Table 1.

Physicochemical measurements: The molar conductance at 25° of the complexes were determined at concentration approximately to 10^{-3} M in dimethyl sulphoxide, except for the Os^{VI} complex where dimethyl formamide was used as solvent. A Philips PR-9500 conductivity bridge was used for measurement. The magnetic moment solid complexes in the powder form were measured by Gouy's method at 300 K employing $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{CNS})_4]$ as the calibrant. The diffuse reflectance spectra were taken on a Zeiss PMQ-II spectrophotometer from the sample diluted with magnesium carbonate and spread on a filter paper. The infrared spectra (nujol) ($4000-400 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) were recorded on a SP-1200 spectrophotometer. Thermogravimetric analyses were made on a Stanton Red Croft 671b thermal analyser.

Results and Discussion

The complexes appear to be thermally quite stable. The molar conductance data revealed that Pt^{IV} and Pd^{II} complexes were nonelectrolytes and Os^{VI} complex was 1 : 4 electrolyte.

The important ir bands, the ligand and the complexes and their tentative assignments were obtained

with reference to the spectra of the other carboxylate complexes as well as those of thio and amino acid complexes¹⁻³. The $\nu_{\text{C-S}}$ band at 725 cm^{-1} of the ligand on complexation does not shift to lower frequency which clearly indicates uncoordinated sulphur. The antisymmetric stretching band on complexation shifted to lower frequencies in the region $1580-1600 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ for these complexes. These values correspond to those of glycinate and other amino acid complexes. The bridging carboxylic groups of metal carboxylate complexes also showed a band in this region. Further, the OH deformation band at 910 cm^{-1} in the ligand disappeared on complexation as the ionisation of the carboxylic group was envisaged on coordination. The observed broad band near 3350 cm^{-1} indicates the presence of water molecule in the Pd^{II} complex. This was further supported by thermogravimetric analysis.

The strong ir band at 850 cm^{-1} in the Os^{VI} complex could be assigned to the ir active $\text{O}=\text{Os}=\text{O}$ stretching mode⁴. A medium intensity band at 1065 cm^{-1} in this Os^{VI} complex could be assigned to the OH bridging vibrations⁵. The band observed at 510 cm^{-1} was assigned to $\text{Os}-(\text{OH})$ stretching mode. The stretching OH vibrations, however, appear as a strong band around 3480 cm^{-1} . This indicates that the two OH groups in the Os^{VI} complex occupy two coordinated positions having a osmyl grouping, thereby making the complex ion of an octahedral stereochemistry. The presence of lattice water was further supported by thermogravimetric analysis.

Pt^{IV} and Pd^{II} complexes with TDSA: The analysis of the Pt^{IV} and Pd^{II} complexes gave 2 : 1 metal—ligand ratio. The diffuse reflectance spectra of the Pt^{IV} complex, displayed a shoulder at 20.00 kK and a maximum at 27.77 kK while that of the Pd^{II} complex showed the lowest energy band at 23.80 kK. These bands could be attributed to metal—ligand (π) charge transfer transitions^{1,2}.

Thermogravimetric analysis of Pd^{II} complex showed initial weightloss at 110° corresponding to one mole of water per mole of the complex. The 3350 cm^{-1} band corresponding to $\nu_{\text{O-H}}$ in the ir spectra of the Pd^{II} complex disappeared on dehydration of the complex at 110° for 2 h.

Os^{VI} complex with TDSA: For the Os^{VI} complex, the present study indicates that the starting material Os^{VIII} gets reduced to Os^{VI} in the alkaline medium and Os^{VI} formed then complexes with the ligand. The Os^{VI}-TDSA complex was found to be diamagnetic in marked contrast to the expected paramagnetism for a d²-system. The diamagnetism of Os^{VI} complex could be explained to be due to the (—COO⁻)₂(O=Os^{VI}=O)(OH⁻)₂ octahedron, which was brought about by the strongly π -donating oxide groups and was sufficient to cause spin-pairing of the t_{2g} electrons in the lower- d_{xy} level⁶. Such a geometry of the Os^{VI} complex was further supported by the reflectance spectrum, which showed three bands at 13.15 kK and 14.28 kK corresponding to the spin-allowed d-d bands and as a charge transfer band at 40.81 kK^{7,8}.

Thermogravimetric data of the Os^{VI}-TDSA complex showed initial weight loss at 120° corresponding to the loss of five moles of water per mole of the complex.

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Nephelauxetic and Hypersensitive Nature of Neodymium(III) Complexes with α -Pyridylthiosemicarbazide and its Furfural-2-aldehyde and Thiophene-2-aldehyde Derivatives

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A new series of octahedral Nd^{III} complexes with recently synthesised α -pyridylthiosemicarbazide (C₆H₈N₄S or 'PT'), *N*-(α -pyridyl)furfural-2-al-

dehyde-thiosemicarbazone (C₁₁H₁₀N₄SO or 'PFT') and *N*-(α -pyridyl)thiophene-2-aldehyde-thiosemicarbazone (C₁₁H₁₀N₄S₂ or 'PTT'), have been isolated and characterised on the basis of their elemental analysis, magnetic and reflectance and ir spectral data revealing 'PT' as bidentate (pyridinic-N and thioketo-S) and 'PFT' and 'PTT' as tetradentate with pyridinic-N, thioketo-S, imine-N and furfuryl-O/thiophenyl-S as donor sites. In the present communication, we report the isolation and characterisation of Nd^{III} complexes with 'PT', 'PFT' and 'PTT' and their nephelauxetic and hypersensitive nature are studied in order to evaluate the stereochemistry of the ligands around Nd^{III} ion.

Experimental

Chemically pure rare earth chloride/nitrate/perchlorate and AnalaR grade chemicals were used throughout. The magnetic susceptibility measurements, reflectance spectra (using MgO as reference), ir spectra (KBr) and far-ir spectra (with CsBr prism using nujol) were recorded as described earlier¹. Elemental analysis for all the present Nd^{III} complexes are found in good agreement with the calculated values, revealing M-L stoichiometric ratio 1:2 (with 'PT') and 1:1 (with 'PFT' and 'PTT'). Nd^{III} ions were estimated by oxalate-formation method². Elemental, magnetic and important ir data are recorded in Table 1, while reflectance spectral bands (cm⁻¹) and relevant parameters in Table 2.

Preparation and isolation of complexes: The ethanolic solution of neodymium hexahydrate trichloride/trinitrate/triperchlorate (10 mmol) were mixed with the refluxing solution of ligand 'PT' (20 mmol) or 'PFT'/'PTT' (10 mmol) in the same solvent. Macrocrystalline and substantially pure products were obtained after refluxing the reaction mixture on a steam-bath for ~40 min (pH 3.5-4.5), which were filtered and then washed successively with ethanol, acetonitrile and finally with small increments of acetone to remove impurities of unreacted ligand and metal ion. All of the complexes were dried completely under vacuum at room temperature and are found insoluble in most of the common organic solvents, viz. DMSO, DMF, dioxane, nitromethane and nitrobenzene, which precluded conductivity measurements and in visible region, reflectance spectra could be undertaken. The presence of ionic chloride/nitrate ions outside the coordination sphere of the complexes were tested by alcoholic AgNO₃ and copper turnings, respectively.

Results and Discussion

Magnetic studies: The values of magnetic moment observed (3.40-3.56 B.M.) for present Nd^{III} complexes having ⁴I_{9/2} ground state term, are closer to those for complexed and free ions as reported by Sinha³ as well as Van Vleck and Frank value⁴ (3.68 B.M.), suggesting octahedral crystal field around the metal ion. A relatively small